

MECHANISMS FOR STRENGTHENING SUSTAINABLE REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT THROUGH INTEGRATED TERRITORIAL INVESTMENTS AND GREEN INNOVATIONS

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***Abstract:** This report examines sustainable regional development as a strategic objective within the policy frameworks of the European Union and Bulgaria, particularly in the context of the European Green Deal and Integrated Territorial Investments (ITI) for the 2021–2027 programming period. It explores the conceptual and institutional foundations of sustainability, as well as the role of green innovations in territorial transformation. Special attention is devoted to ITI as a tool for addressing regional challenges through territorially targeted financing. A case study from the Southeast Region of Bulgaria is presented, illustrating green solutions and their impacts on the economy, environment, and social cohesion. Based on this, recommendations are formulated for local and national authorities.*

***Keywords:** sustainable development; regional policy; integrated territorial investments; green innovations; European Union; territorial planning; green transformation*

1. Introduction

Sustainable regional development constitutes one of the central themes in contemporary European political and academic discourse, particularly in the context of the Green Transition, digitalization, and the pursuit of territorial cohesion. The European Union, through its Cohesion Policy and strategic initiatives such as the European Green Deal (European Commission, 2019), places sustainability at the core of its programming for the 2021-2027

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period, aiming to achieve balanced development across all territories-including remote, rural, and industrially vulnerable regions (Territorial Agenda 2030, 2020).

The COVID-19 pandemic, alongside ensuing economic and social disruptions and the growing risks associated with climate change, has underscored the need for a transformative approach to regional governance. It has become increasingly urgent to identify solutions that not only address environmental challenges but also promote social equity and economic resilience at the local level (OECD, 2021).

In this regard, Integrated Territorial Investments (ITI) have emerged as a key instrument for implementing place-based approaches grounded in the specific needs and potentials of individual territories. Introduced through Regulation (EU) No. 1303/2013, ITIs enable the coordinated use of funding from multiple sources to achieve integrated objectives within a given region (European Commission, 2014). In Bulgaria, for the 2021–2027 programming period, ITIs have been deployed across six functional zones at the NUTS3 level, with an emphasis on partnerships with local authorities, stakeholder engagement, and territorial programming (MRDPW, 2022).

In parallel, green innovations-including technologies for renewable energy, circular economy models, sustainable transport, and digital transformation-are viewed as fundamental drivers of territorial transformation. They play a critical role in achieving the EU's goals for decarbonization and climate neutrality by 2050 (EEA, 2021).

In this context, the present report aims to analyze the potential for synergy between Integrated Territorial Investments and green innovations as a dual mechanism for achieving sustainable regional development in Bulgaria. The study focuses on:

- the institutional and policy frameworks of ITI and the green transformation;
- best practices and challenges in their implementation;
- impact assessment through a case study of a specific project.

Methodologically, the research employs a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches:

- critical analysis of strategic documents of the EU and Bulgaria (ESIF, Green Deal, Regional Development Strategy);
- review of academic literature and comparative European practices;
- empirical case study of an ITI project in the Southeast Region of Bulgaria, involving green technologies and public-private partnerships.

The approach is interdisciplinary and is grounded in the concept of “place-based integrated development” as developed by Barca et al. (2012) and further expanded upon in recent research by the European Smart Specialisation Platform (S3 Platform, 2023).

2. Theoretical Context of Sustainable Regional Development

The concept of sustainable development was firmly established in international political and academic discourse through the report *Our Common Future* by the World Commission on Environment and Development (Brundtland Report, 1987). According to this report, sustainable development is defined as "development that meets the needs of the

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present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs." This necessitates a balanced integration of three fundamental pillars: economic growth, social equity, and environmental protection.

In a regional context, sustainable development implies a place-based approach that takes into account territorial diversity, as well as the cultural, economic, and natural resources specific to each area. The so-called "integrated territorial approach" has emerged as a leading paradigm within the European Union's cohesion policy (Barca et al., 2012). This approach promotes decentralization, partnership-based governance, and the implementation of integrated development strategies.

Key Indicators of Sustainable Development:

The assessment of sustainable regional development relies on a complex system of quantitative indicators, grouped into three main categories:

Economic indicators: Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita, employment rate, labor productivity, share of innovation in the regional economy.

Environmental indicators: greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, levels of air and water pollution, biodiversity, share of renewable energy sources.

Social indicators: poverty rate, access to healthcare and education, social inclusion, demographic structure.

According to reports by the OECD (2020) and EUROSTAT, sustainability is increasingly monitored through the so-called multidimensional Well-being Index, which reflects quality of life beyond purely economic measures.

Figure 1: Key Indicators of Sustainability at the Regional Level

The following graph illustrates regional disparities across selected key indicators of sustainable development at the NUTS-2 level:

As shown, the regions differ significantly in terms of economic development (GDP), environmental pressure (CO₂ emissions), and social infrastructure (access to basic services). These disparities must be taken into consideration in the design of policies and funding instruments such as Integrated Territorial Investments (ITI).

The Interrelationship Between Sustainability, Territorial Development, and Innovation:

Sustainable development cannot be achieved without the adoption of innovation—both technological (e.g., green technologies, digital solutions) and institutional (e.g., new forms of governance, participation, and coordination). Regional development, particularly in peripheral or economically vulnerable areas, requires adaptation to global challenges through local resources and knowledge (Rodríguez-Pose, 2018).

In this regard, green innovations and place-based investment tools (such as ITI) are mutually reinforcing, creating the conditions for a circular economy, social engagement, and energy efficiency within the framework of regional governance.

3. Political and Institutional Frameworks for Sustainable Development

Sustainable development represents a leading strategic paradigm in contemporary policies of the European Union and its Member States, including Bulgaria. At the European level, the political and institutional framework is defined by a number of key documents and mechanisms aimed at achieving climate neutrality, social justice, and territorially balanced development. The central document in this regard is the European Green Deal, adopted by the European Commission in 2019, whose main objective is to transform Europe into the first climate-neutral continent by 2050 (European Commission, 2019). The Deal integrates a wide range of policies from energy and transport transformation to biodiversity conservation and the circular economy. Particularly significant are the Fit-for-55 package (European Commission, 2021), the EU Taxonomy Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2020/852), and the recently adopted Nature Restoration Law, which introduces binding targets for ecosystem restoration by 2030 (European Parliament, 2024).

In 2025, political dynamics within the EU led to intensified debate around the so-called "omnibus" deregulation packages. As a result, parts of the Green Deal were temporarily suspended under pressure from conservative and industrial lobbies (The Guardian, 2025; AP News, 2025). This includes delays in adopting directives against misleading environmental claims (Green Claims Directive) and in revising corporate sustainability reporting requirements under the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) (Reuters, 2025). Nevertheless, the European Commission continues to implement initiatives such as the Clean Industrial Deal, launched in 2025, which promotes clean technology industrial zones through investments in renewable energy, sustainable production, and digitalization (European Commission, 2025).

The Just Transition Mechanism (JTM), managed through the Just Transition Fund (JTF), supports territorial transition efforts, targeting regions with high carbon dependency (European Commission, 2020). Also of great importance are the Horizon Europe programme and the Territorial Agenda of the EU 2030, both emphasizing place-based and

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inclusive policy approaches (Council of the EU, 2020). The European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) oversees over €50 billion invested in sustainable infrastructure and environmental projects (CINEA, 2024).

At the national level, Bulgaria has also established strategic frameworks aligned with European priorities. The National Development Programme “Bulgaria 2030”, adopted in 2020, outlines five strategic goals and thirteen priorities, grounded in the United Nations’ Sustainable Development Agenda (UN, 2015) and European initiatives (Council of Ministers, 2020). Among these, a central role is played by the priority on Sustainable Regional Development, operationalized through the National Strategy for Regional Development 2021–2027 (MRDPW, 2021). The strategy emphasizes Integrated Territorial Investments (ITI) as a key instrument for implementing place-based projects that combine economic, social, and environmental objectives. Funding through ITI mechanisms amounts to 2.5 billion BGN, targeting urban mobility, energy efficiency, and digital public services (MRDPW, 2023).

Another essential component of the national framework is the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP), financed through the EU’s Recovery and Resilience Facility, with a total budget exceeding €5.6 billion (Ministry of Finance, 2024). This plan supports investments in green transformation, digital infrastructure, and social resilience. Within this mechanism, Bulgaria has initiated the implementation of just transition plans for the most affected regions-Stara Zagora, Pernik, and Kyustendil-envisaging measures for reskilling, innovation, and social adaptation of local communities (European Commission, 2024).

An integrated aspect of sustainable development is the Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialisation (ISIS 2021–2027), which promotes regional innovation ecosystems through digitalization, low-carbon technologies, and interregional cooperation (Digital Innovation Hub Bulgaria, 2023). Reports from the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) from 2025 highlight Bulgaria’s progress in implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), while also noting the need for stronger monitoring and accountability regarding business practices and the green transition (UNECE, 2025).

In summary, the political and institutional frameworks for sustainable development in Bulgaria and the EU demonstrate a high degree of strategic alignment and institutional compatibility. Despite existing risks of political setbacks and delays in reforms, mechanisms such as ITI, JTM, and CSRD provide a foundation for effective and inclusive implementation of sustainability as a guiding principle in socio-economic development.

Table 1. Integration of Sustainable Development Goals in the European and National Context

Sustainable Development Goal	European Instruments	National Implementation in Bulgaria
Climate Neutrality	European Green Deal, Fit-for-55, Clean Industrial Deal	National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP), National Energy and Climate Plan
Nature Restoration	Nature Restoration Law	Preparation of a national plan, ITI projects in ecologically vulnerable areas

Sustainable Development Goal	European Instruments	National Implementation in Bulgaria
Social and Territorial Transition	Just Transition Mechanism (JTM), Just Transition Fund (JTF)	Just transition plans for coal-dependent regions (Stara Zagora, Pernik, Kyustendil)
Financing and Accountability	EU Taxonomy Regulation, CSRD, CINEA	Smart Specialisation Instruments (ISIS), ITI, national monitoring systems
Innovation and Digitalization	Horizon Europe, Digital Europe	ISIS Strategy, NRRP components for digitalization

4. Integrated Territorial Investments as a Mechanism for Sustainable Development

Integrated Territorial Investments (ITI) represent an innovative tool for territorial development, introduced by Regulation (EU) No. 1303/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down common provisions on the European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF). ITI enable the combination of resources from various funds-such as the European Regional Development Fund, the Cohesion Fund, and the European Social Fund-with the aim of achieving an integrated approach to sustainable territorial development (European Commission, 2014).

A key advantage of ITI lies in their ability to support the implementation of regional strategies that transcend administrative and sectoral boundaries, promoting coordinated and synchronized actions among different governance levels and stakeholders. This is particularly relevant in the context of the European Cohesion Policy, whose overarching objective is to reduce regional disparities and foster sustainable economic growth (Bachtler et al., 2017).

In Bulgaria, the ITI mechanism is applied within six functional zones at the NUTS 3 level, identified based on demographic, economic, and spatial criteria. Each of these zones comprises a cluster of municipalities centered around a leading city that serves as a functional hub (Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, 2023). A central emphasis is placed on the involvement of local authorities, businesses, the non-governmental sector, and civil society in the planning, prioritization, and implementation of investment projects, in line with the principles of partnership and multi-level governance (European Committee of the Regions, 2019).

Despite its potential, the implementation of ITI in Bulgaria faces a range of practical challenges. These include limited administrative capacity at the local and regional levels, weak institutional coordination among participating bodies, and insufficient expertise in the design and implementation of complex territorial strategies (World Bank, 2022). Furthermore, the lack of systematic impact analysis and monitoring hinders the ability to assess the actual contribution of ITI to sustainable development (OECD, 2020).

Nevertheless, experience from the previous programming period demonstrates that ITI can serve as an effective instrument for regional transformation, particularly when combined with strategic spatial planning, well-developed integrated territorial strategies, and enhanced

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participation of local stakeholders (ESPON, 2021). According to the European Commission (2022), the success of ITI largely depends on the presence of a clear territorial development vision, institutional stability, and the commitment of all actors involved.

In this context, ITI should not be viewed merely as a mechanism for the allocation of funds, but rather as a strategic tool for regional transformation through integrated interventions aligned with social, economic, and environmental objectives, in accordance with the principles of sustainable development and territorial cohesion (Zaucha & Świątek, 2019).

5. The Green Transformation and Innovations in Regional Policy

The green transformation represents a systemic change in economic and social models aimed at achieving sustainable development, a low-carbon economy, and the preservation of natural capital. It is implemented through the integration of ecological innovations, digital technologies, and policies that promote sustainable territorial development (European Commission, 2019).

Green innovations are defined as novelties in products, services, production, or management processes that lead to a significant reduction in negative environmental impact and improved resource efficiency (OECD, 2011). They encompass a wide range of technologies and practices, with renewable energy sources (solar, wind, and geothermal energy), smart grids, sustainable construction, energy efficiency, and circular economy models playing a central role (European Environment Agency, 2020).

In the context of regional policy, green innovations are perceived as a tool for addressing territorial imbalances by creating new market niches, strengthening local economies, and enhancing regional competitiveness. The deployment of green technologies has a multiplier effect—not only reducing environmental footprints but also creating employment opportunities, particularly in the renewable energy sector, green construction, and sustainable mobility of Young Specialists (Tanakov, N. 2024).

Digital transformation is playing an increasingly crucial role in advancing the green transition at the regional level. Technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence, big data, and urban infrastructure management platforms support the development of so-called “smart cities.” These solutions enable efficient energy consumption management, optimization of transportation networks, intelligent waste management, and improved air quality (GeSI, 2019; United Nations, 2022). As a result, territories that successfully integrate digital and green innovations become attractive destinations for investment and job (European Committee of the Regions, 2020).

From a strategic perspective, the instruments of the European Union’s Cohesion Policy, such as the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and the Just Transition Fund, play a vital role in supporting green and digital transformations in less-developed regions (European Commission, 2022). This aligns with the objectives of the European Green Deal, which emphasizes the attainment of climate neutrality by 2050.

Case Study 6: Southeastern Region – Green Industrial Transformation through Integrated Territorial Investments (ITI)

In the context of a territorial approach to sustainable development, Bulgaria's Southeastern Region—encompassing the functional zone of Stara Zagora – Sliven – Yambol—emerges as a leading example of green industrial transformation facilitated through the mechanism of Integrated Territorial Investments (ITI). Within this framework, a strategic project has been launched to establish an energy self-sufficient industrial park oriented toward carbon neutrality and a circular economy.

The project envisions the development of a high-tech industrial zone primarily powered by renewable energy sources, particularly solar energy, through photovoltaic installations equipped with integrated energy storage systems. Additionally, the initiative includes a large-scale facility for the recycling and recovery of industrial waste, aiming to minimize waste streams and promote the secondary use of raw materials in the production cycle (Ministry of Economy and Industry [MEI], 2022).

Financing is secured through a combination of resources from the Regional Development Programme (OPRD 2021–2027) and the Industry Fund, with further mobilization of private investment planned via public-private partnership (PPP) schemes (MEI, 2022; World Bank, 2023). In this context, ITI serves not only as an instrument for territorial cohesion but also as a catalyst for innovation policy at the local level, capable of transforming the region's industrial structure toward a low-carbon economy.

The anticipated outcomes of the project include a reduction in carbon emissions by more than 30% by 2030, in line with the targets of the National Decarbonization Strategy and the Recovery and Resilience Plan (MEI, 2022). Furthermore, the project aims to create sustainable and well-remunerated employment, with a focus on attracting and retaining young professionals in the fields of energy, environmental science, and digital technologies. In this process, collaboration with research and academic institutions plays a key role by providing technological expertise and facilitating knowledge transfer.

The project is further supported by the implementation of a digital platform for the management and coordination of all stakeholders—local authorities, industrial partners, the scientific community, and civil society. The platform aims to ensure a transparent, integrated, and data-driven decision-making process, as well as real-time monitoring of progress toward environmental and social goals (World Bank, 2023).

The synergy between the green transition, digitalization, and the territorial approach positions this initiative as a model for sustainable regional transformation and local-level implementation of the principles of the European Green Deal. It illustrates how strategic investments directed through ITI can address regional disparities and foster sustainable employment and economic renewal by aligning environmental and social objectives.

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

Integrated Territorial Investments (ITI), when combined with the implementation of green innovations, represent a strategic instrument for achieving sustainable and inclusive regional development. When aligned with national and European objectives, this approach

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holds significant potential to address both territorial disparities and structural challenges characteristic of peripheral and underdeveloped regions (European Commission, 2022).

The application of ITI enables the mobilization of diverse funding sources and stakeholders—including the public sector, academia, private enterprises, and civil society—for the development of integrated solutions that foster innovation, sustainability, and social cohesion (OECD, 2021). The incorporation of green innovations within this model further enhances its transformative capacity, particularly in the context of the European Green Deal and the overarching goal of climate neutrality by 2050 (European Green Deal, 2019).

Despite these opportunities, the implementation of ITI frequently encounters significant obstacles, including administrative inefficiencies, insufficient stakeholder coordination, and underdeveloped systems for monitoring and evaluation (ESPON, 2020). In order to enhance the effectiveness and impact of ITI in the context of the green transition, the following actions are recommended:

Recommendations:

Strengthening administrative and institutional capacity at local and regional levels – Targeted investment is required to enhance the capabilities of local administrations, including through training, digitalisation, and the reinforcement of strategic planning processes. This will facilitate more effective ITI management and reduce bureaucratic burdens (European Court of Auditors, 2021).

Broader engagement of universities, research institutions, and businesses – The involvement of academia and the private sector in strategic planning, innovation development, and technology transfer is essential for achieving a genuine green transformation. Mechanisms such as public-private partnerships and regional innovation platforms can facilitate this engagement (Nikolov, G. 2018).

Systematic implementation of monitoring, evaluation, and good practice sharing mechanisms – The application of clear performance indicators, regular impact assessments, and policy adaptation based on empirical data is critical for the long-term effectiveness of ITI. Frameworks such as the Theory of Change and logical models for evaluation are recommended (EVALSED, European Commission, 2013).

Enhanced coordination between regional policy and climate policy at both national and European levels – Climate objectives must be effectively integrated into regional development strategies, including through the application of the Do No Significant Harm principle and alignment with National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) (European Commission, 2021).

In conclusion, the integration of territorial investments with sustainable innovation models requires not only technical expertise, but also strategic vision, political commitment, and the active participation of all stakeholders. Only through a holistic and evidence-based approach can true sustainability and socio-economic transformation of the regions be ensured.

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МЕХАНИЗМИ ЗА ЈАЧАНЈЕ ОДРЖИВОГ REGIONALNOG RAZVOJA KROZ INTEGRISANE TERITORIJALNE INVESTICIJE I ZELENE INOVACIJE

Rezime: *Ovaj izveštaj razmatra održivi regionalni razvoj kao strateški cilj u okviru politika Evropske unije i Bugarske, postavljen u kontekstu Zelenog dogovora i Integriranih teritorijalnih investicija (ITI) za programski period 2021–2027. Istražuju se konceptualne i institucionalne osnove održivosti, kao i uloga zelenih inovacija u teritorijalnoj transformaciji. Posebna pažnja posvećena je ITI kao alatu za suočavanje sa regionalnim izazovima kroz teritorijalno orijentisano finansiranje. Predstavljen je studijski primer iz Jugoistočnog regiona Bugarske, koji ilustruje zelena rešenja i njihov uticaj na ekonomiju, životnu sredinu i socijalnu koheziju. Na toj osnovi formulisane su preporuke za lokalne i nacionalne vlasti.*

Ključne reči: *održivi razvoj; regionalna politika; integrisane teritorijalne investicije; zelene inovacije; Evropska unija; teritorijalno planiranje; zelena transformacija.*